

AGEING OF BIOPOLYMERS REINFORCED BY ALTERABLE GLASS FIBERS

N.Pons, A.Bergeret, J.C.Benezet, L.Ferry
Ecoles des Mines d'Alès – Centre des Matériaux de Grande Diffusion
6, Avenue de Clavières, 30319 Alès, France
Nicolas.Pons@ema.fr

SUMMARY

This study focuses on the ageing of biocomposites made of a biodegradable polymer Poly(Lactic Acid) and alterable glass fibers. Mechanical properties evolution was observed and degradation phenomena were determined. For the short times, ageing was attributed to the interface degradation that is less damaged than the fibers.

Keywords: Biocomposites, hygrothermal ageing, alterable glass fiber, Poly(lactic acid).

INTRODUCTION

At the present time, polymer materials are now starting to face different problems. First, the oil price is not stable and varies significantly generating threats upon the business of polymers. Secondly, the oil availability predictions indicate that the known supplies of oil sustain the current rate of consumption for approximately 50 years. Finally, polymers need long times (bio)degradation (between four and five hundred years).

Today, the bio-based polymers begin to appear in the everyday life as supermarket bags or medicinal applications... This polymer family represents a great interest because it is based on a renewable carbon source and the biodegradation kinetic is fast.

To improve the mechanical properties of biopolymers, a new generation of biocomposites is currently developed. These materials are generally based on a biopolymer matrix reinforced by natural fibers. Natural fibers have the same benefits as biopolymers: they are renewable and biodegradable. Moreover, they are cheap and have a low density. Unfortunately, their mechanical properties are generally low and vary depending on the production location and the climatic condition.

Our project aims to develop a poly(lactic acid) (PLA) matrix reinforced by alterable mineral (glass) fibers. These alterable glass fibers (AGF) have been used with the aim to obtain reinforcements and to be degradable by water and mineralized by microorganisms. This alterability combined to a good reproducibility of glass properties compared to vegetable fibers makes these fibers an interesting reinforcement system with an important potential of development [1, 2]. Alterable phosphates glasses were already used as reinforcement for medical applications.

In this study, ageing of PLA/AGF biocomposites was analyzed and ageing phenomena were determined. Indeed, as the glass fibers are alterable, biocomposite ageing depends on the fibers degradation kinetic. A hygrothermal ageing test was performed to accelerate the degradation. Mechanical tests, weight measurements, thermal analyses and SEM observations were carried out to characterize ageing phenomena.

MATERIALS

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) in the form of small-size granules was commercially available from Nature Works LLC (Blair, USA) under the trade name PLA 7000D.

Three different glass fibers (10 μm diameter) were provided by OCV Reinforcement Co. (Chambéry, France). E-glass is a typically non alterable glass fiber sized with a coating containing a film former agent able to create good interactions with polyester resins. F1 and F2 are AGF developed by OCV Reinforcement. These fibers were coated with different sizing formulations. Different coupling agents and film former were selected.

BIOCOMPOSITE PRODUCTION

Biocomposites (70% PLA/30% AGF in weight) were prepared by extrusion/injection molding. Specimens according to ISO 527-2 standard were produced.

According to NatureWorks PLA 7000D data sheet, pellets were dried for 12h at 50°C under vacuum before they were extruded and injection molded.

A co-rotative twin-screw extruder (Cletral BC21) was used to perform compounding. A uniform temperature (170°C) and a constant screw rotation speed (250tr/min) were used. The polymer matrix was fed at 2.8kg/h and the fiber was manually fed at 1.2kg/h. After extrusion, the material is cooled in a water bath and cut to form pellets.

A Sandretto Co. (type 95 tons) set up was used for injection molding. The temperatures in the screw and in the injector were set to 170°C; the temperature in the mold was 40°C. The main parameters are given in *Table 1 (cf publi EAC)*.

EXPERIMENTATION

The biocomposites mechanical properties were measured through tensile tests (ultimate stress) and impact tests (toughness).

Thermal properties were analyzed by DSC (Differential Scanning Calorimeter) measurements. The glass transition and melting temperatures and the crystallinity ratios were determined.

Hygrothermal tests (65°C, 100 RH.) were carried out on the biocomposites. The mechanical properties (tensile and impact tests) were determined after several ageing times (2, 6, 24, 48, 120 and 240h).

Water absorption (weight measurements) and crystallinity ratios (DSC) were also studied to determine the involved degradation phenomena. SEM observations were carried out to show the evolution of the fracture mechanisms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Ageing of Pure PLA

DSC results for pure PLA (*Figure 1*) exhibit a strong increase in crystallinity ratio from 4 to 32%. Two steps were clearly highlighted. Firstly, from 0 to 48h ageing, a large

increase was measured (from 4 to 25%). Secondly, a continuous slight increase (from 25 to 32%) was measured up to 240h ageing time.

Figure 1: Evolution of pure PLA crystallinity during hygrothermal ageing test.

The crystallinity increase is probably due to two different phenomena. On one hand, as the ageing temperature is above the PLA glass transition temperature (T_g), the macromolecular chains reorganization is easier. On the other hand, while the PLA hydrolysis occurs, the polymer chains size may decrease. The mobility of shorter chains allows easy rearrangements that lead to chemicrystallization.

During hygrothermal ageing, PLA had absorbed water following two steps (*Figure 2*). Between 0 and 120h, a classical water diffusion phenomenon was observed. The water absorption reaches 0.74% after 24h and stays constant until 120h, according to a fickian diffusion law. Then after this ageing time, a big increase of water absorption is detected linked to an osmotic cracking phenomenon. Here, the cracks play the role of water diffusion highways.

Figure 2: Pure PLA water absorption during hygrothermal ageing test.

Figure 3 represents the evolution in strength and impact during hygrothermal ageing. During the first 6h ageing time, tensile strength and impact resistance exhibit a small increase (tensile strength: 72 to 76MPa; impact resistance: 31 to 33kJ/m²). Then, mechanical properties decreased slightly to 120h ageing times. Finally, a significant decrease was observed after 120h ageing time. According to DSC and water absorption results (Figures 1 and 2), different ageing steps may be considered.

Figure 3: Evolution of tensile strength and impact resistance of pure PLA.

Between 0 and 6h ageing times, water absorption is the main ageing phenomenon. The presence of water molecules in PLA matrix induces a slight plasticizing effect. This plasticization is visible on the impact resistance evolution.

Then, to 6 from 120h ageing times, crystallinity increased considerably. Even if the PLA plasticization and hydrolysis took place during this time interval degrading the mechanical properties, the increase of crystallinity allows preserving a high level of tensile strength and impact resistance.

Finally, after 120h ageing time, PLA hydrolysis became the most important ageing phenomenon. Crystallinity still increases (Figure 1) but water absorption reveals an important osmotic cracking (Figure 2). Autocatalysis of PLA degradation probably takes place in the sample core.

Ageing of Composites

Now, the study focuses on composites hygrothermal ageing and the involved mechanisms. Influence of fiber, granulometry of the film former and coupling agent nature was studied.

1) Fiber nature influence

E and F1 glass fiber reinforced PLA biocomposites behaviors in an hygrothermal environment were compared. E and F1-glass fibers were coated by the same sizing.

Composites crystallinity curves (*Figure 4*) follow the same trend than that of pure PLA (*Figure 1*). As for pure PLA, crystallization seems to present two steps.

Figure 4: Composites crystallinity and water absorption during hydrothermal ageing test (◆E-S, ○ F1-S, ● F2-S).

Water absorption results were represented taking into account the PLA fraction (70% in mass) and exhibit interesting information. Depending on the glass fiber nature (alterable or not), the quantities of water absorbed by the composites are different. Both composites based on F1 and F2 AGF presents the higher quantities of absorbed water. If we compare these results with pure PLA water absorption (*Figure 2*), it is interesting to note that composite reinforced with E-glass fiber has adsorbed a lower quantity of water. Here, the E-glass, which is non-alterable, played the role of barrier. In the opposite case, with F1 and F2 AGF, PLA fraction has absorbed more water than pure PLA. So AGF were implied in the water diffusion kinetic.

Figure 5: Evolution of composites normalized strength and impact resistance during ageing test (◆E-S, ○ F1-S, ● F2-S).

To represent the fiber nature influence on the mechanical properties evolution, results were normalized following the Equation 1:

$$NVt_x = Vt_x/Vt_0 \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

Where NVt_x represent the normalized value for x hours of ageing time, Vt_x the absolute value for an ageing time of x hours and Vt_0 being the value before ageing.

For the composite reinforced by E-glass fiber, the tensile strength exhibits a short decrease (*Figure 5*) until 120h ageing time and then a drastic drop to 240h ageing time. This trend is very close to that of pure PLA (*Figure 3*). Here, it can be considered that the fiber is not degraded. Nevertheless, the decrease of impact resistance indicated a sizing degradation. This degradation corresponds to the short decrease of strength between 0 and 120h ageing times.

For the two biocomposites, an important decrease of both mechanical properties was observed (*Figure 5*). This is due to the degradation of the F1 and F2 AGF. Although this fiber induced more water absorption, it provides a stronger reinforcement over time. In this way, after 48h ageing time, biocomposites based on F2 AGF presented higher mechanical properties compared to those of composites based on F1 AGF.

To conclude, a composite based on non-alterable E-glass fiber exhibits decreased mechanical properties with ageing time only because of the PLA matrix and the sizing degradations. For the biocomposites, phenomena are more complicated, because the fibers are degradable too.

Figure 6: Normalized tensile strength evolution and water absorption depending on the granulometry of the film former used in the sizing (♦ F1-01 [100µm], ◊ F1-02 [40µm]).

2) Influence of the granulometry of the film former agents.

Film formers with different polymer particles diameters (40 and 100µm) were prepared and deposited on F1 AGF, the coupling agent being the same.

The use of sizing with a higher particles diameter may involve lower ageing resistance for the composite. Evolution of normalized tensile strength reveals a lower protection for the composite with the highest diameter. This phenomenon is noticeable (*Figure 6*) for the short ageing times ageing, between 0 and 48h where the decrease of strength was more important with a diameter of 100µm. Then for long ageing times, composite with

the highest diameter is still the less protected. This is due to the F1 AGF degradation which becomes the predominant ageing process.

Concerning water absorption, until 48h ageing time, no influence of the particles diameter was revealed. But for 120h and 240h ageing times, higher amount of absorbed water were measured with the higher diameter. This result is probably due to some voids on the fiber surface corresponding to unsized area.

3) Influence of the coupling agent nature used in the sizing formulation.

a- F1 AGF

Three different couples of silanes based on epoxy (ESi), amino (ASi), polyazamide (PAz) and méthacryloxysilane (MSi) were used. Silanes were deposited on F1 AGF, the film former ageing being the same. *Table 1* resumes the different sizing used.

Composite	F1-02	F1-03	F1-04
Silane n°1	PAz	ESi	ESi
Silane n°2	MSi	ASi	MSi

Table 1: Sizing formulations used for F1 glass fiber.

Mechanical properties evolution reveals that the sizing based on ESi-MSi blend provides the best protection (*Figure 7*). After 120h ageing time, it allows to preserve 40% of tensile strength and impact resistance. The worse is based on PAz-MSi.

Figure 7: Normalized tensile strength evolution and impact resistance evolution depending on the nature of the coupling agents used (■ F1-02, □ F1-03, ● F1-04).

At 240h ageing time, all composites present very low properties. Here, the sizing seems not to be involved and the fiber degradation is the main phenomenon occurring in the ageing process.

Figure 8: Water absorption during hygrothermal ageing depending on the nature of the coupling agents used (■ F1-02, □ F1-03, ■ F1-04).

Weight measurements (*Figure 8*) showed no great differences between the different materials. Nevertheless, the sizing (ESi)/(MSi) may absorb less water. Thus, a relationship might be made between hydrophilicity of the sizing, water absorption and composite mechanical properties degradation.

b- F2 AGF

Four different couples of silanes were based on epoxy (ESi), amino (ASi), sulfuro (SSi) and méthacryloxysilane (MSi). Silanes were deposited on F1 AGF, the film former ageing being the same. Table 2 resume the different sizing used.

Composite	F2-01	F2-02	F2-03	F2-04
<i>Silane n°1</i>	ESi	ESi	MSi	MSi
<i>Silane n°2</i>	ASi	MSi	ASi	SSi

Table 2: Sizing formulations used for F2glass fiber.

It may be difficult to conclude about the influence of the coupling agent influence. Mechanical properties (*Figure 9*) and water absorption (*Figure 10*) data exhibit no difference between composites.

Figure 9: Normalized tensile strength evolution and impact resistance evolution depending on the coupling agents used (\square F2-01, \blacksquare F2-02, \blacksquare F2-03, \blacklozenge F2-04).

However, for a 240h of ageing, a decrease was observed. This was attributed to a release of degradation product of the F2 fiber.

Figure 10: Water absorption depending on the nature of the coupling agents used (\square F2-01, \blacksquare F2-02, \blacksquare F2-03, \blacklozenge F2-04).

CONCLUSIONS

Hygrothermal ageing (65°C, 100H.R.) of pure PLA and PLA/AGF biocomposites was studied. Crystallinity, water absorption and mechanical properties were analyzed.

For pure PLA, different phenomena were observed. For the ageing short times (0 to 6h), the main ageing phenomenon is the plasticization due to water molecules diffusion. Then, between 6 and 120h ageing times, an increase in crystallinity allows protecting the mechanical resistance. Finally, after 120h ageing time, the PLA hydrolysis becomes the main ageing process.

The glass fiber nature plays the most important role in the composite degradation in presence of water. A comparison study carried out on non-alterable E-glass fiber and F1 and F2 AGF showed that composite reinforced with E-glass exhibits a behavior close to

those of pure PLA. With F1 and F2 AGF, their different alterability kinetic gives different decrease in properties trends. F2 seems to imply a more important properties reduction for the short ageing times (0 to 24h) and then a better protection.

The role of particles diameter of the film former was demonstrated too. Decreasing this diameter (close to those of the fiber diameter) allows to apply a more homogenous surface treatment. So, the fiber protection is improved.

Finally, the influence of different coupling agents was studied. Silane hydrophilic nature seems to be one of the main parameters controlling the degradation. The use of less hydrophilic molecules reduces the ageing. However, as the biocomposites were based on AGF, after long times of ageing (240h) the sizing do not play any role.

PERSPECTIVES

Now, the study will focus on the sticking agent influence. Different polymers are used to improve the mechanical properties of unaged material and to reduce the degradation during ageing.

Then, to complete these results, the study of the viscosimetric macromolecular weight and SEM analysis will be performed. X-ray measurements could give additional information about the crystallinity.

Finally, a complementary smoother ageing test (immersion in deionized water at 23°C) will be carried out to reduce the fiber degradation influence on the mechanical properties decrease.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors want to acknowledge ADEME (French Agency of Environment and Waste Management) and ANR (National French Agency of Research) for their financial supports. The authors are also gratefully embedded with CEA (French Agency for Nuclear Power, Marcoule, France) and OCV Reinforcement International Co. (Chambery, France).

References

1. I. Ahmed, M. Lewis, I. Olsen, J.C. Knowles, *Phosphate glasses for tissue engineering: Part 2. Processing and characterisation of a ternary-based P_2O_5 -CaO-Na₂O glass fibre system*, *Biomaterials* 25 (2004) 501–507.
2. I. Ahmed, A.J. Parsons, G. Palmer, J.C. Knowles, G.S. Walker, C.D. Rudd, *Weight loss, ion release and initial mechanical properties of a binary calcium phosphate glass fibre/PCL composite*, *Acta Biomaterialia* 4 (2008) 1307–1314.